

Figure S1 Average values of mitochondrial oxygen consumption curves obtained by Seahorse XFp Analyser. (a) – cells were treated with 60 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ of PC AqEP, or with Pg-AqEP, or 2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ of PC for EEP for 24 hours in normoxic conditions; (b) – after the same treatment in hypoxic conditions (2% oxygen). The data are presented as averages of 3 experiments \pm standard deviation.